

AN EXPLORATION FOR TEST METHODOLOGY OF ZONED BLOCK STORAGE DEVICE ON EMULATION PLATFORM AND COMPARISON WITH NON- ZONED DEVICE

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ABSTRACT

Recently, memory device technologies have evolved very fast, and the need for fast benchmarking and testing methods became critical. So, simulation and emulation methods have become very helpful in testing, benchmarking and consequently developing such storage devices. These emulation platforms can be purely software, purely hardware or a mix of both. In this project, a purely software emulation platform is used to test and benchmark zoned and non-zoned block memory devices that constitute the main storage component in Solid State Drives (SSDs). This project explores the use of Linux null block device driver to measure and compare the latency and performance of zoned and non-zoned block memory devices on both real and virtual machines.

By varying the size of Input Output (I/O) and the number of writing threads/jobs, different experiments were run on real machine as well as virtual machines with variable number of CPU cores. Input Output operations (I/Os) are the user data represented in host read/write commands and is used to count the number of completed I/O operations where a typical data size is 512B, 4KB, 8KB, etc. The Flexible Input output (FIO) tester and fio-plot were used for benchmarking. The results show that the performance and latency measurements are better on real machines than on the virtual ones and that there are variations based on number of cores used by the virtual machines.

Storage devices continue to evolve and so the ability to test, benchmark and assess these devices should evolve and adapt to new tools and methods. The use of FIO tools,

benchfio and fio-plot is one way to simplify this task and support the fast evolution of these storage devices.

Keywords: Memory devices, benchmarking, simulation, emulation, SSDs, zoned devices, non-zoned devices, Linux null block, latency, performance, I/O size, CPU cores, FIO, fio-plot.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Solid-State Storage devices are a type of memory device that comprises of host interface and NAND gate blocks. The host interface is accessed through the Operating System drivers which send data (write to the device and read memory from the device) and control signals to the device. The host needs to create a write or read command along with the user data buffer and send the command to the device. In the case of write command, the device processes the write command and reads the data from host memory and then stores it into NAND memory. In the read case the device takes the read command and provides the user data to the host memory. These read/write operations are referred to as Input Output commands (I/Os). To manage the data internally, SSD performs internal operations including Flash Translation Layer (FTL) and garbage collection (GC). Flash Translation Layer is a mechanism which decides how the Logical Block Addresses (LBAs) are mapped to physical memory page (i.e., NAND Pages). The Garbage Collector (GC) algorithm internally manages the NAND memory available and keeps track of available spares which are the NAND memory pages that are available for use or have been reclaimed by the GC.

The below figure-1 shows the typical SSD internal architectural diagram with host setup. The host system is where the OS (Operating System), the driver and the application run. Host and SSD are connected through Peripheral Component Interconnect Express (PCIe) bus to the host interface of SSD. The device uses the PCIe interface to fetch the command and data from host memory.

The device reads the host data and places it into the DRAM buffer. The device then stores the data into the NAND Flash arrays which can read and write the data in parallel.

Figure 1: SSD Internal architectural blocks with Host System

Figure 2: SSD Flash memory arrays

The following terms are important to understand the overall operation of storing data in zoned and non-zoned SSDs:

- Write Amplification is a phenomenon when the host needs to do one write operation, the SSD internally may issue more than 1 write to its NAND media to complete 1 write operation then that is defined as Write Amplification (WA). The ideal Write Amplification Factor (WAF) is 1 where there is no extra write to NAND than the actual writes. NAND is divided into pages and blocks, one block contains many pages, host writes to the device by

pages. If the WAF increases, it means the device life is decreasing as the NAND cell life is limited and there are limited number of erase cycle can be done to NAND device.

- Zone is a contiguous range of logical block addresses (LBAs) that are managed as a single unit.
- LBA is the smallest addressable data unit for Read and Write commands.
- Zoned Namespace (ZNS) is a device that puts restrictions on how the host writes

I/O command should be delivered to ZNS device. Zoned namespace brings the NAND device erase block characteristics to host level and takes advantage of the sequential write. In NAND Erase block, writing is possible only in sequential order; to write a new data, erase block must be erased before a new data can be written again to that block. And there is limitation on NAND device that we can write only limited number of times to the NAND device.

The Solid-State Devices come in zoned and non-zoned types or conventional types. In conventional types, data is scattered across the storage area in the device. In zoned types, the data is organized on the device by the host (e.g., it is the operating system driver system) which has larger control over data placement on the storage device. This offloads the device garbage collection (GC) functionality to the host and makes the device simpler and more cost effective. The below figure-3 is about the data placement, the different color represents scattered data in conventional storage device whereas the data organized in zoned storage device is represented by the color in solid block.

Figure 3: Data placement, Conventional(non-zoned) Vs. Zoned device

Figure 4: Data Placement control

A storage device can have multiple namespaces. Each namespace is a collection of Logical Block Addresses (LBAs) where each one is a relative location in the device where user data is placed. A zoned namespace is divided into equal sized zones, which are contiguous nonoverlapping ranges of logical block addresses. In the figure below, the LBAs (Logical Block Addresses) start from 0 to z-1 and it is taken by the Zone 0, Zone 1 ... Zone x-1 Zones in ZNS (zoned namespace) device is a set of separation of device space. It also shows the allocation of LBAs across the zones in the device. A group of LBAs falls under one zone only and zoned devices place the data in an organized manner whereas the non-zoned devices place it in random manner. Since the zoned device places data in an organized manner into the NAND flash and its Garbage Collection algorithm does not have to work hard as its Write Amplification Factor (WAF) will be lower. In non-zoned device the GC needs to work more to organize the data before it can be placed in the NANDs which slows its average performance. Below is an illustration of zone and LBA relationship.

Figure 5: Zone & LBA relationship

For example, this how the LBAs are distributed below:

Zone 0 has LBA 0, 1,2 ...m-1.

Zone 1 has LBA m, m+1 ... n-1. So, the LBAs are continuous from Zone 0 to Zone 1.

Total number of Zones x -1.

Zone Size = 64MB (Total capacity)

Zone Start LBA = ZS * Zone Index

Zone Capacity = 60MB (writable capacity)

Zoned Namespace Terminologies

The figure below is for a state machine that represents the internal working of a zoned device.

Figure 6: Zone State Machine

The state machine keeps track of the state the device is in and can go through the following different states depending on operation being requested from host machine:

- Zone Empty (ZSE): Accepts write, Read returns the predefined data and has Valid Write pointer.
- Zone Full (ZSF): Valid Writes but not valid pointer.
- Zone Closed (ZSC): Valid Write pointer.
- Zone Implicitly opened (ZSIO): Accepts write, read before Write pointer returns valid data else the predefined one. Valid Write pointer.
- Zone Explicitly opened (ZSEO): Accepts write, read before Write pointer returns valid data else the predefined one. Valid Write pointer.
- Zone Read only (ZSRO): Valid Writes but not a valid pointer.
- Zone Offline (ZSO): Valid Writes but not a valid pointer.

Each zone maintains a write pointer that indicates the next writeable logical block address in that zone. By moving the write pointer across the zone and before reaching the zone capacity, the device will be in an empty state and ready to be implicitly or explicitly opened and written to.

Figure 7: Zone organization layout (example)

Below are the definitions of the zone organization layout:

- Starting point: Starting LBA for zone, i.e., smallest LBA of that zone.
- Write Pointer: Pointing to the next writable LBA location in the zone.
- Zone Capacity: It is the writable capacity of a specific zone; the host can write it too.
- Zone Size: This includes the zone capacity and has some more space but needs to be power of 2. In the above example 4MB is the space which the host cannot write.

2. EMULATION SETUP

Without the need physical devices, emulation/simulation platforms and tools can help validate a design, develop and benchmark a device in a cost-effective way. For this project device emulation was used to evaluate performance measures of actual devices.

Emulating Block Memory Devices

There are multiple ways to emulate block memory devices including:

- null_blk driver

null_blk driver provides the simplest way to emulate a zoned block device with different zone configurations, with Sequential Write Requested (SWR), Using this driver, it is possible to create the zoned device and non-zoned device.

- scsi-debug kernel block device driver

Using this driver too, it is possible to create the zoned device, but it only makes it possible to create emulated SCSI ZBC hard disks.

- tcmu-runner SCSI device emulation

This application uses a regular file as its storage back store. It can emulate hostaware and host-managed ZBC SCSI disks.

- QEMU open-source machine emulator

QEMU supports the emulation of NVMe zoned namespaces devices but getting this up and running is overly complex. Within a guest VM, an emulated ZNS device acts like a physical device.

- null_blk driver (chosen for experiment)

For this project the Linux null_blk driver is used as this is readily available and can be compiled and build with less dependency, The supporting library are easily available and was relatively less complex than QEMU setup and as QEMU has many dependencies on other Linux

packages, which is chain reaction kind of as it asks one after another while installing the package.

Tools Used

The tools used in this project are Zoned Block Device (ZBD) libraries and viewer, Flexible Input Out Tester (FIO), bench-fio, and fio-plot.

- ZBD Library and Zone Operation Command

ZBD library is helpful in creating and managing the zoned device. Below are the operation commands performed on the zoned device:

- Open Zone: Explicitly open zone, means resources are given.
- Reset Zone: Reset the write pointer to starting LBA of zone, Erase the zone data, zone state is empty.
- Close Zone: Transition to closed state.
- Finish Zone: Zone is in Full state and irrespective if write pointer.
- Report Zone: List the zone descriptor. Zone descriptors is a descriptor which describes the Zone attributes.
- Append Zone: It is Write command except that only sequential writes can be issued to zoned device. zoned device cannot accept the I/O out of order whereas the normal NVMe Solid State Drives accepts.

In this case the host serializes the I/O and sends it at once to device. So, the onus is on host to make the data serialize and send it to the device. By doing so host data processing has increased and caused more CPU overhead but it offloads GC operation of device. At the same time, host is not expected to open maximum number of zones as this requires maximum number of resources to be active in device. So, there should be some balance between the Maximum Open Resource (MOR) and Maximum Active Resource (MAR).

MOR is the maximum number of open zones in the zoned namespace whereas MAR is maximum number of active zones in the zoned namespace.

- Flexible IO Tester (FIO):

Flexible IO Tester (FIO) is a benchmarking and workload simulation tool for block devices in Linux. It is highly tunable, and an industry standard too and widely used for storage performance benchmarking. FIO can take a range of parameters for generating I/O patterns.

Using multiple threads/jobs mapping to multiple CPU cores, that is, it can create threads as specified by the user, such as I/O data size, Type of I/O data pattern, whether it is sequential I/O or random I/O. There are more parameters that can be specified are number of threads to create and can specify the test run time, means how long the test should run and then provides the vital I/O statistics for the test run.

Flexible Input Out Tester (FIO) can specify the type of I/O pattern and the most used ones or common ones are below:

--ioengine=str

1. This argument defines how the job issues I/O to the test file. There is a large amount of ioengines supported by Fio, few are mentioned here.
2. libaio – Linux native asynchronous block level I/O.
3. solarisaio – Solaris native asynchronous I/O. Suitable for testing on Solaris.
4. posixaio – POSIX asynchronous I/O. For other Unix based operating systems.

5. windowsaio – Windows native asynchronous I/O in case testing is done on Windows OS.
6. nfs – I/O engine supporting asynchronous read and write operations to NFS from user space via libnfs.

--rw=str

1. read: sequential reads
2. write: sequential writes
3. randread: random reads
4. randwrite: random writes
5. rw: sequential mix of reads and writes
6. randrw: random mix of reads and writes

Fio defaults to 50/50 if mixed workload is specified (rw=randrw).

--rwmixread=

More specific read/write distribution can be configured with this parameter. For example, --rwmixread=30 would mean that 30% of the I/O will be reads and 70% will be written.

--bs=int

Defines the block size that the test will be using for generating the I/O. The default value is 4k and if not specified, the test will be using the default value.

--numjobs=int

The number of threads spawned by the test.

--iodepth=int

Number of I/O units to keep in flight against the file. That is the amount of outstanding I/O for each thread.

The platform taken here is Linux on virtual machine and Linux on actual real machine. Virtual machines are easily available and simple to host and teardown compared to the real machine. Scaling the CPUs to virtual machine is easy whereas the real machine is fixed. But in certain case it is needed to use the real hardware machine. Both zoned and non-zoned block devices were used to evaluate both performance and latency on all testing platforms.

- bench-fio and fio-plot

Bench-FIO is a wrapper tool for FIO and provides features to capture the I/O statistics in multiple json files format and groups which is then used by fio-plot tool for drawing graphs and plots. The appendix has more on how to use the bench-fio and fio-plot tools.

Achieving Performance

The device internally has the parallel mechanism to write/read the data to its NAND memory device. Numjobs is the parameter which controls how many I/O job threads will start. These job threads are responsible for initiating the I/Os to the device and their completion.

The queue depth and number of jobs parameters are used in the bench-fio tool to evaluate the performance and latency in the different experimental setups. Queue depth indicates the number of I/O slots that can be submitted to the device. For example, in a queue depth of 1, only one I/O can be submitted to device and until that I/O completes, the host cannot submit another I/O command. To push more I/O operations then a bigger qdepth is needed. So when the queue depth is small, the device will be idle most of the time as there are not enough I/Os to fetch. Hence the host cannot take advantage of device maximum I/O performance capability. By increasing the qdepth, the device can fetch more commands and load the device's internal

pipeline which improves device throughput that is measured in I/O per second (IOPS). As the qdepth increases, a greater number of jobs (numjobs) are needed to submit the I/Os simultaneously to device. So, by increasing the qdepth and the numjobs, the host will take advantage of device internal parallelism.

Setup Terms

The following table recaps and defines the tools and technical terms introduced so far.

Terms	Definitions
FIO	Flexible Input Output tester
I/O	Input output data commonly referred for Read, or Write data
numjobs	Number of jobs/threads the FIO utility creates for starting the I/Os
qdepth	For async I/O engine mode, how large a queuing depth is maintained
Nonzoned device	Conventional storage device can accept random read and write
zoned device	zoned device, requires the Write to be sequential only (i.e., Sequential Write Required)
SWR	Sequential Write Required
latency time	Time needed to issue a I/O by the job until the FIO job gets the completion response from device. Usually measured in milli seconds(ms) or micro(us) seconds
bench-fio	Wrapper for FIO tool for data generation for fio-plot tool
fio-plot	Plots the data generated by the bench-fio tool
ZBD	Zoned Block Device
ZNS	Zoned Namespace

3. EXPERIMENTS & RESULTS

The experiments were designed to evaluate the latency of zoned versus non-zoned devices and measure their I/O performance. Latency is the time taken by an I/O operation, from its submission by an application to a device until the device responds back with its completion. FIO is the I/O initiator to the device, and it gets the I/O completion notification as well. Performance is measured as number of I/Os per second, i.e., how many I/Os are complete per second or how many notifications are sent from the device to the application through FIO. A typical latency unit is milli/micro/nano second whereas the performance is measured in Kilobytes/Megabytes/Gigabytes per second. These are industry standard units for storage device performance and latency measurements. It is expected that zoned devices will have better latency and performance than non-zoned devices.

The initial plan was to emulate both zoned and non-zoned block devices on Linux virtual machines (VMs). When performance appeared to be affected by the number of CPU cores allocated for the VM, a decision was made to see the effect of running the tests on a real

machine. So we emulated the zoned and non-zoned devices on a real Linux machine with 8 cores. This led to running the benchmark experiments on different test environments:

1. Virtual machine with two CPU cores: data captured in this setup had slow performance and higher latency than expected.
2. Virtual machine with 10 CPU cores: the data collected reflected better performance and lower latency than the previous environment.
3. Real Linux machine with 8 CPUs: the benchmark data was consistent with the second environment and better than benchmark data from the first environment.

In all 3 cases, FIO benchmark was used to vary the number of jobs (numjobs: 1, 2, 4, 8, 16, 32, 64) and queue depth (qdepth: 1, 2, 4, 8, 16, 32, 64) and capture the performance and latency data. numjobs represents the number of FIO threads that initiates the I/O to the device whereas the qdepth represents the number of I/Os being submitted by each FIO thread/job.

Virtual Machine (2 Cores)

Latency is the time difference between when the I/O command (with user data, in this case 4KB each) placed in the queue and when the I/O completed to bench-fio. For example, in zoned->Latency table below, 1 numjobs and for 1 qdepth the latency is 4.02 microsecond.

Performance is how many I/O commands (with user data, in this case 4KB each) are completed per second. For example, in zoned->Performance table below, 1 numjobs and for 1 qdepth the performance is 228KB/s.

The tables below show the latency and performance for the 2 devices (zoned and nonzoned). The last set of tables show the difference in latency and performance between the 2 devices.

Zoned																	
		QDEPTH (q) =>									QDEPTH (q) =>						
		1	2	4	8	16	32	64			1	2	4	8	16	32	64
numjobs(n)	1	4.02	9.14	18	36	107	137	282		1	228	205	216	216	146	228	221
	2	8.66	9.72	17	44	79	182	320		2	218	390	443	328	390	321	372
	4	15	17	34	82	141	301	683		4	216	345	368	364	334	341	356
	8	34	33	81	149	289	556	1020		8	204	347	364	368	374	381	362
	16	69	88	138	232	454	815	2154		16	197	307	341	367	408	403	372
	32	142	207	349	542	1170	3143	5069		32	207	300	303	364	354	286	320
	64	270	412	860	1334	2708	6530	11000		64	199	287	284	332	321	288	321
	Latency (us - microsecond)									Performance IOPS(KB/s)							
Non-Zoned																	
		QDEPTH (q) =>									QDEPTH (q) =>						
		1	2	4	8	16	32	64			1	2	4	8	16	32	64
numjobs(n)	1	4.95	9.86	19	33	83	139	235		1	186	195	205	241	191	228	254
	2	6.34	11	21	50	83	172	353		2	293	328	364	309	372	356	349
	4	11	22	46	83	188	342	793		4	321	349	341	318	334	360	298
	8	21	33	68	125	243	434	1191		8	309	410	446	489	508	565	383
	16	38	59	107	189	321	555	1016		16	334	435	489	551	705	824	830
	32	86	111	221	373	587	1031	2075		32	323	441	514	626	817	975	946
	64	171	306	428	673	1167	2065	4145		64	317	406	566	730	830	967	909
	Latency (us - microsecond)									Performance IOPS(KB/s)							
Difference																	
		QDEPTH (q) =>									QDEPTH (q) =>						
		1	2	4	8	16	32	64			1	2	4	8	16	32	64
numjobs(n)	1	0.93	0.72	1	-3	-24	2	-47		1	42	10	11	-25	-45	0	-43
	2	-2.32	1.28	4	6	4	-10	33		2	-75	62	79	19	18	-35	23
	4	-4	5	12	1	47	41	110		4	-105	-4	27	46	0	-19	58
	8	-13	0	-13	-24	-46	-132	171		8	-105	-63	-82	-121	-134	-184	-21
	16	-31	-29	-31	-43	-133	-260	-1138		16	-137	-128	-152	-184	-297	-421	-458
	32	-56	-96	-128	-169	-583	-2112	-2994		32	-116	-141	-211	-262	-463	-689	-626
	64	-99	-105	-432	-641	-1541	-4485	-6855		64	-118	-119	-282	-398	-509	-679	-588
	Latency (us - microsecond) Delta = (Non Zoned - Zoned)									Performance IOPS(KB/s) Delta = (Zoned - Non Zoned)							

Figure 8: Latency and Performance data for 2 core virtual machine
The non-zoned device outperformed the zoned one in almost all cases.

Figure 9: Latency difference fio-plot for 2 core virtual machine

The above latency difference shows the negative number, which means that the nonzoned device has lower latency than the zoned device which was not expected. This, we believe, is attributed to the following 2 reasons:

- The small number of cores where there are not enough CPU cycles to allow the operating system to run without affecting the threads that need to vary the number of jobs and queue depth.
- In zoned devices, I/Os are processed in sequential manner only whereas the nonzoned device can accept and process the I/Os in random out or order which may affect the latency for zoned devices.

The below figure shows that the performance difference and it is affected too. More numbers are negative and that is because the latency is higher for non-zoned devices in many readings taken below.

Figure 10: Performance difference data for 2 core virtual machine

Due to the above reason, decided to provision more cores to the virtual machine.

Virtual Machine (10 Cores)

In the second test environment, the number of cores on the virtual machine was increased to 10. The same set of experiments were repeated to collect the performance and latency benchmark data reported in the below tables.

In this table, a positive latency number means that the latency of zoned device is lower than that of a non-zoned device, which indirectly says that the provisioning the more core helped to reduce the latency of zoned device than of non-zoned device. In the performance difference table, the numbers are positive and in almost all the cases except a few, which means that the performance is better compared to the non-zoned devices.

Zoned												
		QDEPTH (q-c)					QDEPTH (q-c)					
		1	2	4	8	16	1	2	4	8	16	
numjobs(j)	1	7.08	15	30	61	74	212	212	212	212	212	
	2	6.91	14	28	60	76	219	446				
	4	8.32	12	28	52	69	177	355				
	8	12	23	38	60	115	209	415				
	16	29	46	71	119	218	312	636				
	32	42	92	139	229	476	632	838				
64	127	184	262	427	924	875	2322					
Latency (us - microsecond)						Performance IOPS(KB/s)						
Non-Zoned												
		QDEPTH (q-c)					QDEPTH (q-c)					
		1	2	4	8	16	1	2	4	8	16	
numjobs(j)	1	8.86	25	35	75	186	380	854				
	2	10	19	35	97	283	284	813				
	4	11	28	43	88	176	344	656				
	8	15	27	35	111	229	439	890				
	16	26	47	89	183	376	679	1315				
	32	51	87	167	312	524	1125	1865				
64	103	193	327	593	981	1668	2825					
Latency (us - microsecond)						Performance IOPS(KB/s)						
Difference												
		Latency					IOPS					
		1	2	4	8	16	1	2	4	8	16	
numjobs(j)	1	1.78	10	5	14	112	19	156				
	2	3.09	5	7	37	207	65	367				
	4	1.68	16	15	36	107	167	281				
	8	3	4	17	51	104	230	475				
	16	-3	1	18	64	158	367	689				
	32	-11	-9	28	93	48	503	967				
64	-24	9	65	166	57	793	563					
Latency (us - microsecond) Delta = (Non Zoned - Zoned)						Performance IOPS(KB/s) Delta = (Zoned - Non Zoned)						

Figure 11: Latency and Performance difference for 10 cores virtual machine

The figures below show the latency and performance difference of fio-plot which is the representation of the difference table prepared above.

Figure 12: Latency difference for 10 cores virtual machine
Positive numbers in the above table shows the lower latency.

Figure 13: Performance difference for 10 cores virtual machine

The performance for the 10 core CPU virtual machine shows that the performance is better than the non-zoned device except that there is some anomaly where the performance has saturated for zoned device and then the performance has lowered. This is because, as the number of IO submission is more, these IOs spend more time in queue and the performance drops, whereas the latency of these IOs increases. The zoned device has Write restriction, that it can perform better with the sequential writes.

Real Machine (8 CPU)

In the third test environment and to rule out any side effect by virtual machine platform, the benchmarking was performed on real Linux machine. The benchmark results were similar to the 10-core virtual machine. The tables below show the latency difference between non-zoned device to zoned device. The difference positive numbers show that latency of zoned devices is lower than that of non-zoned ones.

		Zoned						
		1	2	4	8	16	32	64
numjobs\q	1	7.08	15	30	62	175	241	698
	2	6.95	14	28	60	119	219	446
	4	9.32	12	28	52	118	177	395
	8	12	29	38	60	107	208	415
	16	29	46	71	119	158	312	434
	32	62	92	139	220	242	622	878
	64	127	184	262	427	302	875	2322
Latency (in-microsecond)								
		Performance IOP(KB/s)						
		1	2	4	8	16	32	64
numjobs\q	1	132	128	132	128	90	130	90
	2	273	269	278	256	264	264	278
	4	395	385	405	475	420	365	395
	8	508	481	720	800	793	636	643
	16	484	633	745	862	3008	971	1066
	32	487	657	851	1028	1116	1155	1200
	64	491	649	868	1063	1872	1406	1263
Latency (in-microsecond)								
		Non-Zoned						
		1	2	4	8	16	32	64
numjobs\q	1	8.86	25	35	75	186	280	854
	2	10	19	35	87	283	284	815
	4	11	28	43	88	176	344	686
	8	15	27	55	111	219	439	890
	16	26	47	89	183	176	679	1315
	32	51	87	167	312	524	1125	1865
	64	103	189	327	583	981	1668	2825
Latency (in-microsecond)								
		Performance IOP(KB/s)						
		1	2	4	8	16	32	64
numjobs\q	1	106	78	111	105	85	112	74
	2	189	187	221	162	111	221	195
	4	295	241	322	312	306	356	314
	8	478	570	565	555	575	570	565
	16	518	539	588	531	567	607	639
	32	565	638	646	695	910	802	926
	64	569	636	750	822	986	1150	1228
Latency (in-microsecond)								
		Difference						
		1	2	4	8	16	32	64
numjobs\q	1	1.78	10	5	13	11	39	156
	2	3.09	5	7	17	164	68	367
	4	1.68	16	15	36	58	167	281
	8	3	4	17	51	112	230	475
	16	-3	1	18	64	208	367	689
	32	-11	-5	28	92	282	503	987
	64	-24	9	65	166	679	793	505
Latency (in-microsecond) Delta = (Non-Zoned - Zoned)								
		Performance IOP						
		1	2	4	8	16	32	64
numjobs\q	1	26	50	23	23	5	38	76
	2	104	72	97	94	356	43	125
	4	100	324	93	168	114	209	222
	8	30	31	155	275	178	66	78
	16	-34	94	157	331	441	364	427
	32	-78	19	205	333	206	353	304
	64	-78	13	118	241	886	256	35
Performance IOP(KB/s) Delta = (Zoned - Non Zoned)								

Figure 14: Latency and Performance difference for 8 CPU real machine

An Exploration for Test Methodology of Zoned Block Storage Device on Emulation Platform and Comparison with Non-Zoned Device

The figure below, shows a difference of latency of non-zoned to zoned device and it shows that in most cases the latency data has been positive, meaning that the zoned device latency is better than the non-zoned one. The latency and performance for the 1 queue dept and number of 16,32,64 are skewed. This is because except one job other jobs are starving to submit the I/O before the previous I/O completes, which could be incurring the average higher latency.

Figure 15: Latency difference for 8 CPU real machine

The figure below is about the performance delta of zoned device to non-zoned device and the positive number shows that performance is on the higher side for zoned device than non-zoned device.

Figure 16: Performance difference for 8 CPU real machine

4. Performance Evaluation and Analysis

The 2core virtual machine test environment highlighted how the performance and benchmark data can be influenced by the number of cores allocated for the VM. With only 2 cores, there were not enough CPU cycles to run the Operating System (OS) and the benchmark application (FIO) simultaneously especially when many threads/jobs are needed. This led to allocating a greater number of CPU cores to the VM.

In the second test environment, 10 cores were allocated to virtual machine which boosted zoned device performance and surpassed that of the non-zoned ones. Now, that the system overhead anomaly is eliminated, the next thing was to verify that this is consistent with the results of a real machine.

This led to the third test environment, in which a real Linux machine with 8 CPUs was used to run the same set of experiments from before. The performance improved as the queue depth (qdepth) and number of jobs (numjobs) increased. There were few cases where performance saturated at some values of numjobs/qdepth pairs and then onwards the performance has dropped. That is expected as the total number of I/Os waiting in the queue is higher but the number of I/O completing are the same which increases the I/O latency. These points in the qdepth vs. numjobs represent the saturation for that matrix where the device performance either remains constant or starts to drop.

In the last 2 test environments, most of the experiment results show that zoned devices have outperformed the non-zoned devices. Since the zoned device (Sequential Write requested-SWR) performs the I/O in sequential manner which is a restriction or limitation for it to perform better as the I/O mapping to exactly maps to media and does not need any other level mapping, the application is expected to do the I/O in sequential manner for zoned-SWR type device, whereas the non-zoned device can do the I/O in sequential or random manner but cannot perform better.

The first 2 core VM test environment has systemic anomaly but, in that case, the zoned device has performed better in some of the cases. Where the 10-core virtual machine experiments exhibit that the performance of zoned devices is better than that of nonzoned ones in almost all cases. And to reconfirm the 8-core real machine experiment also shows that the zoned device is performing better in case of SWR case always. The zoned device performance saturation over the increasing the queue depth(qdepth) with number of jobs(numjobs) has been justified.

5. FINDINGS AND CONCLUSION

This project is an exploration of methods to test zoned devices and how to benchmark the performance. An emulation tool was chosen as it is cost effective and easy to setup and tear down. Benchmark results were collected using different tools that included Flexible Input Output tester (FIO), bench-fio and fio-plots.

To validate the benchmark results, many experiments were run on several test environments that were setup using real Linux machine as well as virtual machines with different number of cores. Initial results pointed the need to have enough CPU cycles to be able to run the host OS as well as the threads needed to simulate parallel write instruction to the device. Experiments were modified where enough cores provided enough cycles to run both the OS and the test tools. To verify the benchmark data a test environment of real Linux machine was used. The results were affirmative and confirmed the results that were obtained using the Linux null block driver are similar on real as well as virtual Linux machines with enough CPU cores. A saturation anomaly was identified when increasing the queue depths and number of jobs beyond a certain point without increasing performance.

We believe this concludes that testing and benchmarking memory devices is possible in emulated environments and that these environments can be effective ways of testing, benchmarking and advancing the design of storage devices.

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